

Synthesis of Fusaric acid and its Derivatives

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A new synthetic method for preparation of fusaric acid and other 5-alkyl picolinic acids has been developed starting from 2-methyl-5-ethynylpyridine. The structure of intermediate products has been established from their mass spectra.

Fusaric acid is a well known natural product possessing a wide range of bacteriostatic and herbicidal activity¹. It is produced by pathogenic fungi fusarium type, causing wilt disease of cotton plant. Activity of fusaric acid has been attributed to its ability to extract heavy metal ions from metal containing enzymes such as succinoxidase and cytochromoxidase². Several methods of synthesis of fusaric acid have been described³⁻⁵; however, they are not of much use in the preparation of homologues. We have found a convenient general method for synthesis of 5-substituted picolinic acids⁶, starting from 2-methyl-5-ethynylpyridine (I) which can be easily obtained from commercial 2-methyl-5-vinyl-pyridine⁷ by bromination and dehydrobromination.

2-Methyl-5-alkynylpyridines (II) were prepared by alkylation of 2-methyl-5-ethynylpyridine (I). Reduction of (II) by Al-Ni-alloy⁸ and oxidation of the resulting 2-methyl-5-alkylpyridines (III) by SeO₂ gave 5-alkyl picolinic acids (IV) in

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good yields. By a similar method 1,4-bis-(6-carboxypyridyl-3)-butane (VI) is obtained from bis-(6-methyl-3-pyridyl-)-diacetylene (V).

The I. R. spectra (KBr) of 2-methyl-5-alkylpyridines did not show absorption bands at 1640-1680 and 2100-2200 cm^{-1} , U V. spectra (in methanol) have absorption maximum at 268 $\text{m}\mu$ typical for alkyipyridines⁹. Mass-spectra of 2-methyl-5-alkylpyridines (Fig. 1) characterised by maximum peak of a fragmentation (m/e 106),

Fig. 1.

formed by cleavage of α , β -C-C-bond of alkyl group. Stability of the ion (VII) is probably due to its rearrangement to the azatropilium ion (VIII). The second important rearrangement peak, m/e 107 (IX), was formed probably by a hydrogen transfer, followed by elimination of olefine. As expected, the intensity of peaks of these ions increases with increasing chain length, Further disintegration of ions (VIII) and (IX) takes place uniformly in all investigated compounds. Elimination of HCN and 2H and formation of ions m/e 79 and 77 (C_6H_7 and C_6H_8 respectively) were indicated. Branching of the carbon chain in 2-methyl-5-isoheptylpyridine is responsible for the formation of a new ion, m/e 163 by cleavage of methyl group. This was not observed in the spectra of straight carbon chain alkyipyridines.

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However, spectra of 2-methyl-5-alkynylpyridines (Figs. 2-5) show formation of

Fig. 2.

main ions at m/e 130 (X) by fission of C-C-linkage in β -position to triple bond¹⁰.

Further elimination of HCN and acetylene was confirmed by the presence of metastable ions. Spectra of higher alkynylpyridines (see Figs. 3-5) show intensive

Fig 3.

10. P. B. Tevent'ev, R. A. Khmel'nitskii et al., *Zhur. Org. Khim.*, 1968, 4, 938.

peaks at m/e 144 and 158 (XI and XII respectively) corresponding to fragments resulting by cleavage of γ - and δ -C-C-bond of alkynyl chain. The abnormal stability

Fig. 4.

Fig 5.

of these fragments is due to the long conjugated chain formed during acetylene butadiene rearrangement of the molecular ion. Such a mechanism, however, requires further confirmation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purity of compounds was checked by thin-layer chromatography on Al_2O_3 (II grade). Using the system benzene-methanol 25 : 1 (Spots were detected by fluorescence in UV-light). The saturated dialkylpyridines found to have R_f 0.56-0.60 and the corresponding acetylenes, 0.40-0.50. Thus this method permits to check the presence of starting material during reduction process and to select correct condition quickly.

For acids paper-chromatography is more used (Whatman type paper "Leningrad B" : butanol-acetic acid-water 75:15:10 ; Rf 0.80-0.85).

2-Methyl-5-alkynylpyridines (II) : Method A : To a freshly prepared solution of sodamide (from 0.15 g. atom of metallic sodium) in liquid ammonia (200 ml) was added with stirring 2-methyl-5-ethynylpyridine (0.15 of mole) and the stirring continued for 3 hr. During the last 15 min. alkyl bromide (0.3 g. mole) was added. Mixture was stirred for another 4 hr, water (200 ml.) added and extracted with ether. The extract dried over anhydrous K_2CO_3 , ether removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to get pure 2-methyl-5-alkynylpyridines.

Method B : To a suspension of powdered sodium (0.05 g. atom) boiling absolute xylene (20ml.) slowly added with stirring 2-methyl-5-ethynylpyridine (0.05 g. mole). During the course of 10 min. the corresponding alkyl *p*-toluenesulfonate (0.05 g. mole) at 70° was added. The mixture was stirred for 3 hr. at 80° , and the alkynylpyridine was isolated from the reaction mixture as described earlier (Method A).

2-Methyl-5-alkylpyridines (III) : To 2-methyl-5-alkynylpyridine (0.019 g. mole) in 20% NaOH solution (30 ml) at 90° Ni/Al alloy (6 g.) was added with stirring in

small lots. Stirring was continued until the evolution of hydrogen ceased, then Ni/Al alloy (1 g.) and 20% NaOH (5 ml.) were added and stirred for another 0.5 hr. It was filtered, the precipitate washed with water and the filtrate extracted by ether. The extract dried and the product was purified by distillation under vacuum.

5-Alkylpicolinic acids (IV) : A suspension of 2-methyl-5-alkylpyridine (0.08 g. mole) and selenium dioxide (0.12 g. mole), pyridine (100 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hr. with stirring. Then it was filtered and washed with hot water ; pyridine was removed by steam distillation, the aqueous solution was filtered again and the filtrate evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The residue boiled with a mixture of CCl_4 and cyclohexane (1 : 1), solvent removed in vacuum and the obtained acid crystallized from heptane.

1, 4-Bis (6-carboxypyridyl-3) butane (VI) : 1, 4-Bis (6-carboxypyridyl-3) butane prepared by heating 1,4-bis (6-methylpyridyl-3) butane (3.6 g.) with selenium dioxide (4.9 g.) for 4 hr. as described above ; yield 1.4 g (36%), m.p. 256-258° (Dioxane water 1 : 1) ; Rf (paper chromatography) 0.13.

(Found : C 63, 50 ; H 5.37, $C_{16}H_{16}N_2O_4$. requires C 63, 98 ; H 5, 36%).

TABLE

	R ¹	R ²	Yield ^a) in %	boiling point (pressure in mm)	n_D^{20}	Formula	Picrate melting point	Lit.
1.	$C_2H_5C\equiv C$	CH_3	70(22)	112°(7)	1,5500	$C_{10}H_{11}N$	160-161° ^b)	—
2.	$C_4H_9C\equiv C$	CH_3	76(41)	136-138°(6)	1,5365	$C_{12}H_{15}N$	144-146° ^c)	—
3.	$i-C_4H_9C\equiv C$	CH_3	70	112°(5)	1,5381	$C_{12}H_{15}N$	166-168° ^d)	—
4.	$n-C_4H_9$	CH_3	87	95°(10)	1,4898	$C_{10}H_{13}N$	133-134°	4
5.	$n-C_6H_{13}$	CH_3	83	130-132°(15)	1,4925	$C_{12}H_{15}N$	120-121°	9
6.	$n-C_4H_9$	COOH	40	m.p. 98-100°		$C_{10}H_{13}O_2N$		4
7.	$n-C_6H_{13}$	COOH	32	m.p. 101-102°		$C_{12}H_{17}O_2N$		9

a) Yield of acetylenes shown by method A ; in brackets by method B.

b) Found : N 14, 94 ; 15, 03 ; requires N 14, 96%.

c) Found : C 53, 59 ; 53, 61 ; H 4, 58 , 462 , requires C 53, 23 , H 4, 58%.

d) Found ; N 13, 94 ; 13, 73 ; requires 13, 93%.

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